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Review Article

**A REVIEW ON MORINGA OLEIFERA TABLETS FOR
DIABETES****Kandagatla Sumanth, Dr.A.Pavani**Department of Pharmaceutics, Sri Venkateswara College of Pharmacy, Hi-tech City Road,
Madhapur, Hyderabad.T.S.- 500081**Abstract:**

Globally, diabetes and its associated neurological consequences are major public health issues. Novel nutritional and therapeutic approaches are required due to the growing number of affected persons. Because of its potential antihyperglycemic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and lipid-regulating qualities, the tree Moringa oleifera (MO) has been utilized as a food source and in traditional medicine. The abundance of phytochemicals found in the tree's leaves, fruits, roots, and oil may help to explain these characteristics. More long-term and chronic research is required, however the evidence for MO extract's acute antihyperglycemic benefits on diabetic animal models appears to be strong. The hypoglycemic effects of MO on people, however, are less evident. This could be explained by the limited number of human trials as well as the wide variety of approaches and MO dosages. Furthermore, there is conflicting information from both human and animal trials about how the MO intervention affects insulin levels. Therefore, to determine whether MO affects insulin activity or levels, further systematic research is required.

Keywords: Moringa oleifera, diabetes, Tablets, metabolism

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1. INTRODUCTION

The tree *Moringa oleifera* (MO), commonly referred to as the "drumstick," is a member of the genus *Moringa* and family *Moringaceae*. It was originally indigenous to the Himalayas but is now grown in many tropical and subtropical areas of the world [1]. Various MO parts, including leaves, fruits, flowers, and roots, have been utilized in traditional medicine and as food [2]. For instance, beta-carotene, vitamins B, C, and E, minerals (calcium, iron, potassium, magnesium, etc.), essential and non-essential amino acids, and carbohydrates are among the numerous nutrients found in leaves, the most widely used portion [3]. In traditional medicine, MO has been used to cure a variety of ailments. More recently, it has been suggested that MO may help with a wide range of illnesses, such as diabetes, cancer, neurological, inflammatory, gastroenterological, and cardiovascular [4]. The enormous quantities of chemicals found in the various tree segments may account for the wide range of uses ascribed to MO. For example, phytochemicals that are extracted from MO seeds, such as glycosidic glucosinolates (GLSs), isothiocyanates (ITCs), nitriles, carbamates, and thiocarbamates, have demonstrated chemopreventive, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and hypotensive effects [5].

In the general population, metabolic and neurological disorders are common and often lead to chronic consequences that significantly impair quality of life. The current increase in the prevalence of metabolic syndrome, diabetes, and related conditions (obesity and cardiovascular pathologies) highlights the need for improved dietary and lifestyle practices as well as the creation of more effective treatment options [6]. Hyperglycemia, a major component of metabolic syndrome, has been linked to the development of neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease as well as significant progressive damage to various organs, including the kidneys, nerves, and retina [7]. It is also a critical factor in the development of diabetes mellitus (DM). The most prevalent peripheral nerve injury caused by diabetes mellitus is diabetic neuropathy, which is characterized by bilateral, symmetrical, distal-to-proximal destruction to the sensory nerves in the foot (in a "stocking-glove" pattern). Globally, it is estimated that 387 million people have diabetes and over 316 million people have pre-diabetes, with about 200 million of these individuals developing neuropathy [8].

Currently, various MO tree components are being studied for potential positive effects on the therapy of metabolic disorders, namely diabetes mellitus. In animal models, MO has been shown to have antihyperglycemic activity [9] and to ameliorate the

consequences of induced diabetes in rats [10]. Additionally, some beneficial effects on the neurological system have been noted in both in vitro and in vivo studies [11]. This paper's primary goal is to discuss the general effects of MO on insulin and glycaemia and to provide pertinent preclinical and clinical data about MO's application in these areas. We have identified DM as a possible treatment target of MO by concentrating on research of the disease in humans and animals.

MO Tree Parts and Overall Mechanisms of Action

2.1. MO Fruit, Seed, and Oil

MO seeds and the oil they produce can be used both commercially and for human use [12]. Niazimicin, sitosterol, niazirin, benzyl carbamate, and benzyl isothiocyanate were found in an ethanolic extract of MO seeds [13]. According to the same study, niazirin exhibited significant antitumoral properties in chemical carcinogenesis. The oil content of MO seeds is over 40%, and they include a lot of fatty acids, such as sterols, tocopherols, and oleic acid, which is thought to decrease cholesterol [14]. The levels of cholesterol, phospholipids, triglycerides, very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and the atherogenic index decreased in rabbits fed MO derived from fruits in combination with lovastatin, but the high-density lipoprotein (HDL) ratio (HDL/HDL-total cholesterol) increased [15]. Furthermore, MO's seeds contain over 30 natural antioxidants, such as kaempferol, which enhances metabolism and cellular function in addition to its antioxidant properties [16]. As was previously indicated, fruits and seeds contain GLSs, ITCs, nitriles, carbamates, and thiocarbamates. These compounds may have other potential uses, such as anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive, antifungal, and antiseptic properties. Additionally, because of their high vitamin C concentration, they may be helpful in preventing scurvy [5,14].

2.2. Leaves

MO leaves are widely used as a dietary item in many parts of the world because they contain both macro- and micronutrients. The leaves contain large amounts of calcium, phosphorus, iron, and manganese in addition to a high protein content (24.8–35.3 g/100 g) [17]. MO leaves have been utilized in traditional medicine to treat a variety of ailments in addition to their nutritional benefits. Beta-carotene, vitamins B, C, and E, polyphenols, phenolic acids, alkaloids, GLSs, ITCs, tannins, saponins, oxalates, phytates, and antioxidants are among the many bioactive substances that are abundant in the leaves [1,18]. Despite the fact that the majority of research on the effects of the compounds found in MO leaves has been done on

animal models, the findings point to potential benefits for a number of human illnesses. In a rat model of induced arthritis, extracts from MO leaves shown antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory properties in a recent study [19]. *Moringa oleifera* polysaccharide 1 (MOP-1), a new arabinogalactan with potent antioxidant qualities, has been extracted from MO leaves [20]. Furthermore, it has been suggested that MO leaves could help with bacterial and viral illnesses [21, 22]. According to reports, MO leaves may help with a number of chronic illnesses, such as diabetes, insulin resistance, cancer, liver disease, and cardiovascular disorders. For instance, the presence of B-sitosterol, alkaloids, tannins, ITCs, quercetin, and chlorogenic acid has been linked to cardioprotective benefits [23].

2.3. Roots and Barks

Both the roots and bark of MO have been utilized by humans, primarily for therapeutic purposes. The MO tree's food value is limited since its roots contain more antinutrients than other portions. In addition to having larger levels of carbohydrates, salt, arginine, lysine, and ascorbic acid (but not thiamine, riboflavin, or pyridoxine), roots also include higher concentrations of tannins and oxalates, which are not beneficial as nutritional sources [24]. The use of bark and roots has demonstrated antiulcer, antisecretory, and cytoprotective properties in animal models [25]. Treatment for impaired vision, joint discomfort, diabetes, anemia, hypertension, toothache, hemorrhoids, and uterine diseases are among the many advantages that have been documented in other studies [1].

2.4. Mechanisms of Action of MO

Every component of the MO tree offers a variety of nutrients and compounds that can have a wide range of impacts on the organism. The mechanism of action of MO extracts' impacts on metabolism—primarily on glucose regulation—will be the main topic of this section.

MO has a number of polyphenols, as was previously mentioned. The phenolic acids caffeoylquinic acid and chlorogenic acid, as well as the flavonoids quercetin and kaempferol, are among the most significant [26]. These substances appear to have antihyperglycemic effects by competitively inhibiting the sodium-glucose linked transporter type 1 (SGLT1) in the duodenum and jejunum, which lowers intestinal glucose absorption [27]. The glucose transporter 2 (GLUT2), which can be drawn to the small intestine basolateral membrane by circulating glucose stimulation, is one of the additional processes involved in glucose

absorption [28]. Because GLUT2 and SGLT1 expression is elevated in DM, the small intestine's ability to absorb glucose is enhanced [29]. The fact that the majority of prevalent antidiabetic medications, such as sulfonylureas, biguanides, or thiazolidinediones, have primary targets on organs other than the intestines adds to the burden on individuals with diabetes mellitus [30]. Because MO lowers glucose levels, it has been researched as an antidiabetic agent. Quercetin is one of the suggested mechanisms because it can function as an apical inhibitor of GLUT2 [31], while having no effect on GLUT5 or SGLT1 [32]. However, quercetin has also been demonstrated to downregulate phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase (PEPCK) and glucose-6-phosphatase (G6Pase) in the liver, increase glucose uptake by stimulating GLUT4 in skeletal muscle, and activate adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK) [33]. It has been demonstrated that MO aqueous leaf extract inhibits the activity of α -glucosidase, pancreatic Intestinal sucrose and α -amylase both contribute to antihyperglycemic effects [34]. The phenols, flavonoids, and tannins found in MO enable these inhibitory actions. A postponement of the carbohydrate

Hemoglobin A1C (HbA1C) and postprandial hyperglycaemia are decreased as a result of digestion brought on by the inhibition of these enzymes. The existence of a 2,3-double bond and an increase in the number of hydroxyl groups on the B ring have been biochemically explained as the cause of these inhibitory effects of flavonoids, such as quercetin and kaempferol [35]. Furthermore, these substances have been investigated for their ability to protect and regenerate pancreatic beta-cells, hence increasing the generation and release of insulin [10]. By phosphorylating the extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) pathway and shielding pancreatic beta-cells from oxidative damage, quercetin promotes the release of insulin [36]. Quercetin and kaempferol are also found in the leaves of the common walnut tree, *Juglans regia*. Protein tyrosine phosphatase 1B (PTP1B), which is responsible for the negative regulation of the insulin-signaling pathway, has been demonstrated to be inhibited by leaf methanolic extracts derived from this tree [37]. Additionally, by inhibiting PTP1B, chlorogenic acid has been shown to improve glucose absorption in myocytes [38]. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that quercetin dramatically raises the activity of hepatic glucokinase, which mediates the conversion of glucose into glucose-6-phosphate (G6P) and is involved in the insulin functional pathway, in diabetic rats (but not in normoglycemic animals) [39].

Because it inhibits G6P translocase, chlorogenic acid also contributes to hepatic gluconeogenesis by reducing glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis [40]. When transition metals are present, hyperglycemia can cause the development of hydrogen peroxide and ketoaldehydes, which speeds up the synthesis of advanced glycation-end products (AGE) [41]. In addition to downstream stimulation of proinflammatory pathways such as nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), AGE causes a variety of consequences, such as cross-linking of critical proteins, changes in protein function, and cell damage from reactive oxygen species (ROS) [8]. A significant amount of glycosylated proteins and AGE is linked to the emergence of long-term diabetic problems, such as neuropathy, nephropathy, retinopathy, and heart-related ailments. It has been demonstrated that polyphenols from an aqueous leaf extract from Missouri prevent protein oxidation, AGE production, and protein cross-linking in glycation processes [42]. It is thought that polyphenols' capacity to scavenge free radicals produced by glycoxidation processes makes them protective against protein glycation [43]. As a result, a number of MO constituents, including kaempferol, quercetin, gallic acid, chlorogenic acid, and ellagic acid, have been investigated as potential defenses against ROS and the oxidation of DNA, proteins, and lipids by free radicals [44–46]. Furthermore, MO treatment decreases the activity of uncoupling protein 2 (UCP2), increases the amount of supercomplexes and complex I activity, and decreases the acetylation of mitochondrial proteins, according to a recent *in vitro* study [47]. This suggests that MO may have antihyperglycemic effects through modulation of the mitochondrial respiratory chain. By functioning as hypolipidaemic and antiatherosclerotic agents, the antioxidant qualities of MO extract agents may help stop lipid oxidation [48]. Apart from its antioxidant qualities, extracts made from the leaves, flowers, and seeds of MO have demonstrated anti-inflammatory properties [49–51]. The presence of flavonoids, phenolic chemicals, and ITCs is primarily responsible for these characteristics. Some of these substances have been demonstrated to have anti-inflammatory properties by reducing nitric oxide synthase (NOS) production and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) activity [52]. The pancreas is one of many organs in diabetes mellitus (DM) that exhibit an excess of mitochondrial superoxides, which raises ROS production and activates pathogenic pathways. These ROS cause oxidative damage, insulin resistance and stress-induced beta-cell destruction in the pancreas. MO extracts decrease

inflammation and oxidative stress by inhibiting the activation of the NF- κ B pathway, which in turn lowers the expression of proinflammatory agents such as inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) [53]. Furthermore, kaempferol therapy has been demonstrated to suppress cellular death in pancreatic beta-cells by reducing caspase-3 activity and enhancing the antiapoptotic response via the phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K)/Akt and cAMP/protein kinase A (PKA) signaling pathways [54].

As a potential hypolipidemic agent, MO has also been investigated. According to reports, an aqueous leaf extract from MO has lipid-lowering qualities via inhibiting bile acid binding, pancreatic lipase, and pancreatic cholesterol esterase, as well as by reducing the creation of cholesterol micelles [34]. Furthermore, increased expression of PPAR α 1 (peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors) Rats given MO seed powder have been shown to exhibit (PPAR α 1) and γ (PPAR γ) [55]. PPAR are vital for cellular energy balance, lipid metabolism, and ketogenesis; they are expressed in the liver, brain, heart, and muscle, among other organs. Moreover, PPAR have a role in glucose control, inflammation, and immunity [56]. MO may therefore aid in regulating lipid metabolism, reducing the long-term negative consequences of conditions like diabetes mellitus and atherosclerosis.

3. Preclinical Proof of MO's Impact on Insulin and Glucose

The potential hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties of MO extracts have been investigated. The mechanism of action and function of MO in chronic illness models as DM have been assessed in a number of animal experiments. Relevant studies on animal models examining the effects of MO extracts on diabetes and glucose metabolism, including reported changes in insulin levels, were included in this review. Out of the 20 publications we discovered, 14 focused on leaves, four on seeds, one on fruit (pods), and one on leaves, seeds, and stem. Rats were utilized in fourteen of the investigations, mice in five, and rats and mice in just one. In one study, MO leaf extract was used to reduce glucose intolerance in male Goto-Kakizaki rats with diabetes and male Wistar rats without diabetes [27]. Compared to control Wistar rats, which showed a nonsignificant decrease in glycaemia after 60 and 120 minutes following glucose injection, Goto-Kakizaki rats showed a significant decrease. MO aqueous leaf extract at varying doses improved glucose tolerance in diabetic rats, decreased glycaemia in controls, and restored normal glycaemia in sub, mild, and severely

diabetic rats, according to a study conducted on male Wistar rats with diabetes induced by streptozotocin (STZ) intraperitoneal injection (i.p.) (55 mg/kg) [60]. The MO extract outperformed glipizide, a sulfonylurea used to treat diabetes mellitus in humans, which was utilized as a positive control in the same trial. The study also found that mice treated with MO had improved hemoglobin and total protein levels, and that their urine contained no proteins or glucose. A methanolic extract from MO fruits was administered to male and female Wistar rats with diabetes that had been brought on by an intraperitoneal injection of 50 mg/kg of STZ [73]. The scientists demonstrated that when diabetic rats were given MO, their blood glucose and nitric oxide levels decreased while their serum insulin, protein, and antioxidant function increased. Glibenclamide, a sulfonylurea frequently used to treat diabetes mellitus in humans, was employed as a positive control in the same trial, and the outcomes were comparable to those of the animals given MO. In a related investigation, MO ethanolic leaf extract outperformed glibenclamide in treating Long Evan rats with STZ-induced (90 mg/kg, i.p.) diabetes, despite the fact that the insulin levels of the diabetic animals were unchanged [9]. These findings were replicated in a subsequent study using diabetic Sprague-Dawley rats treated with MO and those treated with glibenclamide, yielding similar outcomes [57].

When MO aqueous leaf extract was administered to female Wistar rats with alloxan-induced (100 mg/kg, i.p.) diabetes, their glycaemia significantly decreased and returned to normal, and their lipid metabolism improved [10]. Additionally, there was proof of hepatocyte and pancreatic beta-cell regeneration following MO therapy. Male Sprague-Dawley rats with STZ-induced (60 mg/kg, i.p.) diabetes who received MO aqueous leaf extract showed a substantial decrease in glycaemia [61]. Additionally, this study demonstrated that MO therapy decreased malondialdehyde (MDA), raised glutathione (GSH), and maintained beta-cell histology. When 50 or 100 mg/kg of MO seed powder was administered to rats with STZ-induced diabetes (60 mg/kg intravenous; i.v.), glycaemia significantly decreased but did not revert to control values [69]. Furthermore, lipid peroxidation, antioxidant enzymes (MDA, catalase, superoxide dismutase (SOD), and GSH), immunoglobulins (fewer IgG and IgA), anti-inflammatory (fewer IL-6), HbA1C, electrolytes (sodium and potassium), and kidney and urinary functions (creatinine, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and uric acid) were all improved by MO treatment, according to the authors. The aforementioned

parameters were significantly improved by both treatments with MO (50 and 100 mg/kg); however, the dose of 100 mg/kg showed to be more beneficial. Other alloxan-induced and STZ-induced diabetes rat models showed comparable antioxidant and hepatoprotective effects [62,65]. Apart from its antihyperglycemic properties, MO extract has demonstrated protective effects on the mitochondria. When given to STZ-induced (55 mg/kg, i.p.) diabetic Wistar rats, MO methanolic leaf extract increased heme oxygenase-1 and GSH levels while decreasing ROS production and lipoperoxidation in the liver mitochondria [66]. In a different investigation, male Wistar rats treated with MO methanolic leaf extract after being given alloxan-induced diabetes (120 mg/kg, i.p.) demonstrated a significant decrease in glycaemia and an increase in insulin levels when compared to the diabetic animals that were not treated [64]. The effects of treatment with MO were comparable to those of treatment with metformin, a biguanide often used to treat diabetes mellitus in people, according to the scientists. Additionally, the same study found that HDL significantly increased while blood total cholesterol, LDL, and triglycerides significantly decreased. Transgenic mice with diabetes have also been used to study the effects of MO. When Tang et al. [68] administered a MO ethanolic extract derived from leaves, seeds, and stem to C57BLKS/J Iar-+Leprdb/+Ledprdb and C57BLKS/J Iar-m+/Leprdb mice, they observed a significant drop in blood glucose levels from day 14 to day 35, along with a significant rise in insulin levels and a significant drop in LDL and triglycerides. When compared to seeds and stem, the ethanolic leaf extract exhibited the strongest antioxidant effects; however, only the leaves' glycaemic effects were examined. Alloxan-induced (150 mg/kg, i.p.) diabetic Wistar rats were shown to benefit from glycaemic reduction through chronic administration (up to 42 days) of MO ethanolic leaf extract in conjunction with sitagliptin, an oral antihyperglycemic used in DM type 2. However, administration of MO alone only resulted in a significant reduction in fasting blood glucose levels on day 21, failing to offer a significant reduction at later times of the study, according to Olurishe et al. [67]. Additionally, the same study found no discernible decrease in insulin levels following treatment with MO extract and no alterations in the pathologic lesions in the retina brought on by hyperglycemia. The same group's related study, which also used alloxan-induced diabetic Wistar rats treated with sitagliptin and MO ethanolic leaf extract, found no improvement in kidney function or structure, a significant increase in urea and triglycerides, and no changes in blood electrolyte or albumin levels (glycaemia or insulin were not

measured) [74]. MO aqueous leaf extract significantly reduced glycaemia in both acute and long-term studies of female Wistar rats with STZ-induced (45 mg/kg, i.p.) diabetes and female C57BL/6 mice with high-fat diet-induced diabetes [63]. It is unclear if the results of this study might have been comparable to those of Olurishe et al. [67], who examined glycaemia up to 42 days, because the chronic effects were only measured up to day 22. Furthermore, MO-treated diabetic rats and mice showed improved hepatic functioning, lower levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and VLDL, and higher levels of HDL. Compared to the rat diabetes model, the effects of the MO aqueous leaf extract were more pronounced in the diabetic mouse model. MO therapy increased glucose tolerance in a trial that fed five-week-old C57BL/6J mice an extremely high-fat diet, causing obesity and insulin resistance [70]. For up to 12 weeks, the animals were fed ad libitum diets that were either very high in fat or low in fat along with an isothiocyanate-enriched MO seed treatment. According to the study, during the course of 12 weeks, mice treated with MO had lower blood glucose levels than mice fed a very high-fat diet without MO treatment. Only in week nine of the trial did the rats fed a low-fat diet exhibit a decrease in blood glucose. Other advantages of the MO treatment, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and gut microbiota regulation, were also mentioned by the authors.

Certain compounds from the MO tree have also been explored, such as niazirinA, S-Methyl-N-{4-[(α -L-rhamnosyloxy)benzyl]}thiocarbamate, and N,NJ-bis{4-[(α -L-rhamnosyloxy)benzyl]}thiourea. for potential antidiabetic and antihyperglycemic benefits in preclinical studies. According to a recent study, the aforementioned chemicals, which were extracted from MO seeds, dramatically lowered blood glucose levels in Institute of Cancer Research (ICR) mice that were diabetic due to STZ (40 mg/kg) [71]. Male diabetic mice given alloxan (150 mg/kg, i.p.) were used to study a protein isolate from MO leaves that contained 57.5% of the soluble protein of the leaf extract [59]. One i.p. protein isolate dosage at 300 In diabetic mice, 500 mg/kg (but not 100 mg/kg) was able to cause a notable hypoglycemia reaction; however, the effect was eliminated when the protein isolate was heated to 98 °C or when it was taken orally. This protein isolate dramatically raised catalase and decreased MDA levels, but it had no effect on insulin or SOD levels. A three-week MO leaf powder therapy (700 mg/kg once daily) was able to enhance oral glucose tolerance test results, as well as lower triglyceride levels and reduce belly circumference in a metabolic syndrome

model created in Wistar rats by feeding them a high-fat diet [58]. Blood pressure, fasting glucose, total cholesterol, and the insulin tolerance test showed no changes.

Prior studies demonstrated that MO has a hypoglycemic effect in a variety of animal models and circumstances. The highest antihyperglycemic effects on diabetic rats were primarily observed between 200 and 300 mg/kg, despite the use of a relatively broad range of MO dosages. With a low value of 20 mg/kg, the study by Wang et al. [71] demonstrated a significant hypoglycemic impact; however, this finding may be explained by the fact that the doses were not comparable because isolated MO compounds were employed in this investigation rather than tree parts. As was previously indicated, these glycemic effects could be explained by a number of MO components. For instance, it has been demonstrated that the flavonoid kaempferol enhances AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) activity, GLUT-4 expression, glucose absorption, glycolysis, and glycogen synthesis [58,75]. The majority of the publications that were found did not report how MO affected insulin levels. Future research should assess insulin levels in conjunction with glycaemia levels, as this is a crucial aspect of DM, to ascertain the total impact of MO on this condition. The evidence supporting MO's ability to modulate insulin is still being examined. In diabetic mouse models, MO methanolic fruit, methanolic leaf, and ethanolic leaf extracts, respectively, increased insulin levels, according to studies by Gupta et al. [73], Olayaki et al. [64], and Tang et al. [68]. Although glycemic levels were not measured in this last trial, a drop in insulin levels was noted in a Wistar rat model for polycystic ovarian syndrome treated with MO aqueous leaf extract [76]. Additionally, Azad et al. [9], Olurishe et al. [67], Paula et al. [59], and López et al. [58] did not report any changes in insulin. The various experimental settings used in the investigations, including different tree sections, animal models, and MO dosages, may account for these discrepancies in the insulin outcomes that were achieved.

4. Clinical Proof of MO's Impact on Insulin and Glucose

Few human clinical trials or research have been carried out, despite the large number of in vitro and animal studies documenting MO's antihyperglycemic benefits. Six published studies that assessed the impact of MO on human blood glucose levels were found during our search. According to a study on postmenopausal women without diabetes, taking 7 g of MO leaf powder orally every day for three months

raised hemoglobin levels and dramatically lowered fasting blood glucose levels [77]. These ladies also had changes in a number of antioxidant markers, showing a significant increase in serum retinol, serum ascorbic acid, glutathione peroxidase, and SOD while a significant drop in MDA. After consuming MO, the authors of this paper reported no adverse or side effects. However, it is unclear whether other dietary or external factors influenced the outcomes because the authors did not disclose whether the background diet was either regulated or monitored. In a trial involving healthy male and female volunteers, increasing oral dosages of MO leaf powder (1 g, 2 g, and 4 g) every two weeks resulted in a considerable rise in blood insulin levels but no discernible decrease in fasting plasma glucose [78]. When the individuals were given 4 g of MO leaf powder, their insulin levels increased the most. Furthermore, following MO use, the scientists found no alterations in BUN, creatinine, alanine aminotransferase (ALT), or aspartate aminotransferase (AST). Following MO intake, no adverse or subsequent effects were noted. It is unclear whether the observed insulin alterations were caused by an outside source because the authors did not specify whether the baseline diet was regulated or monitored. The levels of fasting plasma glucose at 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes after ingesting 500 mg of MO aqueous leaf extract were not significantly altered in another investigation conducted on healthy male and female volunteers [79]. Acute alterations were noted in other areas, though, with a notable rise in antioxidant markers and a notable drop in MDA levels. In addition to maintaining their usual diet, level of physical activity, and overall lifestyle throughout the trial, participants were instructed to fast for at least eight hours prior to MO consumption. Additionally, there were no discernible changes in glycaemia or HbA1C levels in a randomized, placebo-controlled clinical investigation that examined the effects of MO leaf capsules and a placebo in individuals with type 2 diabetes who had not yet received treatment [80]. Over the course of four weeks, the patients were given 4 g of MO leaf powder capsules twice a day, before breakfast and before dinner. Despite the fact that four patients experienced temporary diarrhea, there was no occurrence of hypoglycemia during MO therapy. Additionally, there were no discernible variations in BUN, creatinine, ALT, or AST. The authors did not specify whether the background diet was tracked or regulated. Another study looked at the effects of a 12-week MO treatment (500 mg three times a day) in DM patients and found significant plasmatic reductions in both HbA1C levels and high specificity C-reactive protein [81]. However, this study has significant limitations, including not reporting changes in insulin

or blood glucose, not employing blinding or randomization in the study design, not identifying the participants' type of diabetes, and having a very wide age distribution, among other things. In addition to preventing smoking, alcohol consumption, and endurance exercise the day before the blood draws, each participant had a home partner who was in charge of keeping an eye on treatment compliance. Last but not least, a recent investigation on type 2 DM and healthy volunteers from a Saharawi people residing in refugee camps revealed that MO consumption significantly decreased α -amylase activity and glycaemia [82]. Glycaemia was measured postprandial at 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180 minutes after the participants' meal, which included 20 g of MO leaf powder. Glycaemia levels in the healthy patients did not significantly change, but in the diabetic subjects, glycaemia levels significantly decreased 90, 120, and 150 minutes after MO therapy. For the participants, the researchers made a special meal consisting of 160 g of camel meat stew and 80 g of rice. As a result, the diet was strictly regulated and consistent for every participant. There was no information on HbA1C or insulin levels.

NCT03189407 and NCT02308683 are two studies that are registered in the clinical trials database of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) in the United States. Both investigations are listed as finished, but no study findings are given. In the study NCT03189407, individuals with type 2 diabetes were given 400 g of MO in tea twice a day along with metformin. Blood glucose levels and variations in metformin plasmatic levels were to be measured in this investigation. In accordance with the publication, study NCT02308683 was conducted on adult DM patients who were given a 12-week MO supplement [81].

5. CONCLUSIONS:

As an antidiabetic, the tree MO has been suggested and investigated. We reviewed human and animal in vivo publications about the potential involvement of MO in diabetes, with an emphasis on glycaemia and insulin alterations.

Glycaemic levels are significantly altered by MO ingestion or therapy. Glycaemia or glucose tolerance tests showed a significant decrease in all of the animal studies that were included of this analysis. The glycaemia of diabetic animals treated with MO was significantly lower than that of diabetic controls in all diabetes animal models, regardless of the kind of extract (powder, aqueous, methanolic, or ethanolic) or the component of the tree (leaves, seeds, or fruit)

employed. More long-term and chronic research is required, however the evidence for MO extract's acute antihyperglycemic benefits on diabetic animal models appears to be strong. This is significant since metabolic syndrome and diabetes mellitus are chronic conditions, and new treatment (or supplemental) drugs must take this into account. The large range of reported parameters is a significant limitation of the research that were included of this review. Specifically, the conclusions on the efficacy of MO therapy in animal models of diabetes are limited by the lack of other supporting tests of glucose metabolism, such as glucagon or glycosylated hemoglobin. Future studies should also look at other glucose function-related indicators in addition to the hypoglycemic effects of MO.

Only two human investigations, one on type 2 DM patients and one on postmenopausal women, demonstrated a substantial reduction in glycaemia in contrast to animal research; the other four, two on healthy subjects and two on DM patients, did not. Since each study employed a distinct methodology and a wide variety of doses, it is challenging to compare these results. In contrast to the other five research, the postmenopausal women's study utilized the most MO and for the longest duration (7 g daily for three months). Many animal investigations did not show a significant drop in glycaemia following the use of MO in nondiabetic controls, as was the case with healthy human subjects. This suggests that glucose management may work better in pathological settings. Determining which phytochemicals (or a combination of them) have acute or long-term glycaemia-lowering benefits may be made easier with a more thorough separation and characterisation of the many phytochemicals found in MO. However, the data suggests that MO consumption is safe for people (between 500 mg and 7 g) and animals (between 50 and 700 mg/kg). According to this safety profile, nutritional studies involving MO as a supplement or complement for patients with neurological or metabolic disorders should be planned. Despite MO's safety profile, its taste may be a problem in human investigations, especially long-term trials, as reports of this tree's low taste acceptability in meals have been made [82]. Furthermore, only a small number of studies employed seeds or fruits; the majority used MO leaves. To ascertain which tree part—or combination of them—is most effective, more comparative research comparing the various tree sections is therefore advised. Compared to the evidence for antihyperglycemic benefits, the evidence for changes in insulin levels brought on by MO intervention is less strong.

Numerous experiments on rats and mice failed to duplicate the considerable increase in insulin levels that other studies demonstrated. Similar results were seen in human investigations, where only one (in healthy subjects) reported insulin, indicating that people treated with MO had significantly higher insulin levels. Therefore, further investigation is required to determine whether MO affects insulin activity or levels. When deciding which kind of diabetes is to be treated with an intervention, this is crucial since type I would benefit from an increase in insulin, whereas type II might not because of hyperinsulinemia. Strong antioxidant and lipid metabolic regulating qualities are among the other effects frequently noted in animal models and human research that are consistent with in vitro findings. These qualities may also be useful in the treatment of a number of neurological and metabolic disorders, including diabetes.

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